

BIR JINSLI BO'LMAGAN KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMA UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI YECHIMI

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Koshi masalasi, Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila, Mittag-Leffler funksiyasi, Dirakning delta funksiyasi.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu ishda kasr tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama uchun qo'yilgan Koshi masalasini Laplas hamda teskari Laplas almashtirishlari yordamida yechish masalasi hamda bu yechimning klassik yechim bo'lish masalasi o'rganilgan.

Masalaning qo'yilishi: Bizga quyidagi bir jinsli bo'lmagan kasr tartibli differensial tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi berilgan bo'lsin:

[D_{0+}^alpha y(x) + lambda y(x) = f(x), x > 0, 0 < alpha < 1
y(0) = y_0

bu yerda

D_{0+}^alpha y(x) = ?

(1) tenglamaning yechimi mavjud deb, uning yechimini topamiz. Buning uchun D_{0+}^alpha y(x) Kaputo ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila uchun lim_{alpha -> +0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) va lim_{alpha -> 1-0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) limitlarni mavjudligini ko'rsatamiz.

1) lim_{alpha -> +0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) = lim_{alpha -> +0} 1 / Gamma(1-alpha) * integral_0^x y'(t) dt / (x-t)^alpha = 1 / Gamma(1) * integral_0^x y'(t) dt = integral_0^x y'(t) dt = y(x) - y(0) = y(x) - y_0

lim_{alpha -> +0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) = y(x) - y_0

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Yuqoridagi integral regularizatsilangan integral bo'lganligi uchun to'g'ridan to'g'ri limitga o'tamiz. Natijada

2) lim_{alpha -> 1-0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) = lim_{alpha -> 1-0} 1 / Gamma(1-alpha) * integral_0^x y'(t) dt / (x-t)^alpha = 1 / Gamma(0) * integral_0^x delta(x-t) y'(t) dt = y'(x)

lim_{alpha -> 1-0} D_{0+}^alpha y(x) = y'(x) = lim_{x -> x_0} (y(x) - y(x_0)) / (x - x_0)

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(3) ifodadan ko'ramizki alpha -> 1 - 0 da klassik hosilani berar ekan.

Bu yerda

(x-t)^{-alpha} / Gamma(1-alpha) -> delta(x-t), (alpha -> 1) - Adamr yadrosi,

yadrosi,

delta(x - x_0) = { 0, x != x_0; infinity, x = x_0 } ^ integral_{-infinity}^{+infinity} delta(x - x_0) dx = 1 - Dirakning deltasi

forall phi in D(R) = C_0^infinity R, integral_{-infinity}^{+infinity} delta(x - x_0) phi(x) dx = phi(x_0), delta(x) = delta(-x)

Koshi masalasi (1) ni yechish 2 ta holatda qarab chiqiladi:

1. $\alpha \rightarrow +0$ holatda (2) ifodani (1) qo'ysak $y(x) - y_0 + \lambda y(x) = f(x)$ bundan esa $y(x) = \frac{1}{1+\lambda} [f(x) + y_0], \lambda \neq -1$

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yechim hosil bo'ladi.

2. $\alpha \rightarrow 1 - 0$ holat uchun (3) ifodani (1) ga qo'ysak

$$\begin{cases} y'(x) + \lambda y(x) = f(x) \\ y(0) = y_0 \end{cases}$$

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(5) tenglama klassik ma'nodagi bir jinsli bo'lmagan Koshi masalasi bilan bir xil ko'rinishga kelib qoldi. Bu tenglamani Laplas almashtirishi yordamida yechilsa quyidagi hosil bo'ladi

$$y(x) = y_0 \int e^{-\lambda(x-t)} f(t) dt$$

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Yuqorida biz $\alpha \rightarrow +0$ va $\alpha \rightarrow 1 - 0$ bo'lgan ikkita holatda (1) bir jinsli bo'lmagan kasr tartibli Koshi masalasining yechimini qarab chiqdik.

Keyingi navbatda esa (1) bir jinsli bo'lmagan kasr tartibli differensial tenglama uchun Koshi masalasining umumiy yechimini topish ketma - ketligini qarab chiqamiz. Buning uchun Laplas almashtirishlaridan foydalanamiz.

$y(x)$ ning Laplas almashtirishi:

$$L\{y(x)\}(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y(x) dx; \text{ Res} > \text{Res}_0; |y(x)| \leq M e^{s_0 x}; M > 0 \quad (7)$$

$y'(x)$ ning Laplas almashtirishi:

$$L\{y'(x)\}(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y'(x) = e^{-sx} y(x)|_0^\infty + s \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y(x) dx \quad 8$$

$\text{Res} > \text{Res}_0; |y(x)| \leq M e^{s_0 x}; M > 0$ shartlarga ko'ra

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} e^{-sx} y(x) \leq \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} e^{-sx} \cdot M \cdot e^{s_0 x} = M \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} e^{-(s-s_0)x} = 0 \quad 9$$

(9) ifodaga ko'ra (8) ifoda quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$L\{y'(x)\}(s) = 0 - y(0) + s \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y(x) dx = sL\{y\}(s) - y(0)$$

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(10) Laplas almashtirishidan kelib chiqib $D_{0+}^\alpha y$ ning Laplas almashtirishini yozamiz $D_{0+}^\alpha y : L\{D_{0+}^\alpha y\}(s) = s^\alpha L\{y\}(s) - y(0)s^{\alpha-1}$. 11

Yuqoridagi Laplas almashtirishlarini (1) tenglamaga qo'yamiz

$$s^\alpha L\{y(x)\}(s) - y_0 s^{\alpha-1} + \lambda L\{y(x)\}(s) = L\{f(x)\}(s). \quad 12$$

Budan

$$L\{y(x)\}(s) = \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \lambda} y_0 + \frac{1}{s^\alpha + \lambda} L\{f(x)\}(s)$$

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ifoda hosil qilamiz va teskari Laplas almashtirishini almashtirishlarini qo'llaymiz.

$$\frac{s^{\beta-\gamma}}{s^{\beta \pm \omega}} \equiv t^{\gamma-1} E_{\beta,\gamma}(\mp \omega t^\beta) \quad - \text{ Teskari Laplas almashtirishi.} \quad 14$$

Bu yerda $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \beta)}$ - Mittag Lefler funksiyasi. (14) ga ko'ra

$$\frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \lambda} \equiv x^{1-1} E_{\alpha,1}(-\lambda x^\alpha) = E_\alpha(-\lambda x^\alpha)$$
$$\frac{1}{s^\alpha + \lambda} \equiv x^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda x^\alpha)$$

Yuqoridagi teskari Laplas almashtirishlariga ko'ra hamda (13) yechim quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$L\{y(x)\}(s) = L\{E_\alpha(-\lambda x^\alpha)\}(s) \cdot y_0 + L\{x^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda x^\alpha)\}(s) \cdot L\{f(x)\}(s); \quad 15$$

$$1. \quad L^{-1}L = LL^{-1} = I$$

$$2. \quad L\{f\} \cdot L\{g\} = L\{f * g\} = L\{\int_0^x f(x-y) \cdot g(y) dy\} \text{ xossalarga ko'ra}$$

$$y(x) = E_\alpha(-\lambda x^\alpha) \cdot y_0 + \int_0^x y^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\lambda y^\alpha) f(x-y) dy; \quad 16$$

yechim hosil bo'ladi.

Keyingi navbatda (16) yechimning klassik yechim ekanligini ko'rsatishimiz kerak. Buning uchun (4) va (6) yechimlarni (16) yechim bilan ustma ust tushishini ko'rsatishimiz kerak bo'ladi.

Birinchi navbatda (16) yechimni Mittag Lefler funksiyasini qo'llagan holda soddallashtirib olamiz.

$$y(x) = y_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda x^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + 1)} + \int_0^x y_0^{\alpha-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda y^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \alpha)} f(x-y) dy = I_1 + I_2$$

$$I_1 = y_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda x^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + 1)} \quad 18$$

$$I_2 = \int_0^x y_0^{\alpha-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda y^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \alpha)} f(x-y) dy$$

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow +0} I_1 = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow +0} \left(y_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda x^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + 1)} \right) = y_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-\lambda)^n = \frac{1}{1+\lambda} y_0; |\lambda| < 1 \quad 20$$

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow +0} I_2 = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow +0} \left(\int_0^x y_0^{\alpha-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda y^\alpha)^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \alpha)} f(x-y) dy \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-\lambda)^n \int_0^x \delta(y) f(x-y) dy = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-\lambda)^n \cdot f(x-y)|_{y=0} = \frac{1}{1+\lambda} \cdot f(x) \quad 21$$

$$y(x) = I_1 + I_2 = \frac{1}{1+\lambda} (y_0 + f(x)) \quad 22$$

Yuqorida $\alpha \rightarrow +0$ da yechimning klassik yechim ekanligini ko'rsatdik. Keyingi navbatda esa $\alpha \rightarrow 1 +$ da (16) yechimning klassik yechim bo'lishini ko'rsatib o'tamiz: $\alpha \rightarrow 1 +$ da Koshi masalasi:

$$\begin{cases} y'(x) + \lambda y(x) = f(x) \\ y(0) = y_0 \end{cases} \quad 23$$

Tenglamani yechish uchun Laplas almashtirishlarini bajarib olamiz:

$$y(x): L\{y(x)\}(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y(x) dx \quad 24$$

$$y'(x): L\{y'(x)\}(s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y'(x) = e^{-sx} y(x)|_0^\infty + s \int_0^\infty e^{-sx} y(x) dx = 0 - y(0) + sL\{y(x)\}(s) = -y_0 + sL\{y(x)\}(s) + \lambda L\{y(x)\}(s) = L\{f(x)\}(s) \quad 25$$

$$L\{y(x)\}(s) = \frac{1}{s+\lambda} (L\{f(x)\}(s) + y_0) \quad 26$$

$$\frac{1}{s+\lambda} \equiv E_{1,1}(-\lambda x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda x)^n}{n!} = e^{-\lambda x} \quad 27$$

Bu yerda $\frac{s^{\alpha-\beta}}{s^{\alpha \pm \omega}} \equiv t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(\mp \omega t^\alpha)$ teskari Laplas almashtirishi.

$$\frac{1}{s+\lambda} L\{f(x)\}(s) = L\{e^{-\lambda x}\}(s) L\{f(x)\}(s) = L\{f \cdot e^{-\lambda x}\}(s) = L\left\{ \int_0^x f(y) e^{-\lambda(x-y)} dy \right\}(s)$$

$$L\{y(x)\}(s) = y_0 L\{e^{-\lambda x}\}(s) + L\left\{ \int_0^x f(y) e^{-\lambda(x-y)} dy \right\}(s)$$

$$y(x) = y_0 e^{-\lambda x} + \int_0^x f(y) e^{-\lambda(x-y)} dy \quad 28$$

(28) yechim 1-tartibli hosila uchun Koshi maslasining klassik yechimi bo'lishi kelib chiqdi.

Xulosa

Yuqoridagilardan xulosa qilib aytsak (16) yechim bir jinsli bo'lmagan kasr tartibli tenglama uchun Koshi masalasining Klassik yechimi bo'lar ekan. Bundan kelib chiqadiki (16) yechimdan biz shu turdagi boshqa tenglamalarni yechishda ham foydalanishimiz mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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